

THE HARM OF CARBONATED DRINKS FOR MEDICINES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12748307>

Relevance: How often do you use soft drinks or other beverages to take your medication? Many people tend to grab whatever drink is convenient when taking their medicine, sometimes using it to mask the bitter taste of tablets. But how safe is this practice? Can these beverages actually cause interactions with medications?

Aim of research: To determine whether it is harmful to take medicines with soft drinks or other beverages.

Results: Soft drinks or carbonated beverages are typically acidic, which can diminish the effectiveness of many medications, particularly their antibacterial properties. When combined with certain medicines, carbonated drinks may trigger allergies or adverse reactions in some individuals. Therefore, it's advisable to completely avoid soft drinks. Additionally, soft drinks can hinder the absorption of iron. Hence, if you're taking iron supplements or medications containing iron, it's not recommended to consume them with soft drinks.

There are some drinks that can be harmful for your health if you drink it with medicines:

1. Milk. Taking antibiotics, such as ampicillin, amoxicillin, chloramphenicol, and tetracycline and ciprofloxin group antibiotics with milk are not recommended. Calcium, zinc, iron, and magnesium in milk can bind certain types of antibiotics and inhibit the absorption of drugs in the intestine. When antibiotics bind to these substances, they can form substances that are insoluble and cannot be absorbed by our body. As a result, the drug becomes ineffective and the healing process takes longer than usual. If you want to drink milk, you have to wait two hours before or after taking medicine.
2. Grapefruit juice. Red grapefruit juice contains chemicals that can bind enzymes in the intestine. When the juice inhibits enzymes, it is very easy for drugs to enter the bloodstream. As a result, blood levels will be faster and higher than normal. In some cases, blood levels that are too high can be dangerous. The best thing to do is to avoid drinking red grapefruit juice along with some blood pressure medications, cholesterol medications, and blood vessel blockages.
3. Soft drinks. Besides containing high sugar levels, consuming soft drinks or carbonated drinks with medicinal drugs can cause allergies or certain side effects. Consumption of drugs with soft drinks can also cause absorption of iron in the body. Therefore, you should avoid taking medicine with soft drinks.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the choice of beverage consumed alongside medication can significantly impact its effectiveness and safety. While soft drinks and carbonated beverages are popular choices, their acidic nature can interfere with the absorption and potency of medications, potentially leading to adverse reactions or diminished therapeutic outcomes. Additionally, beverages like milk and grapefruit juice contain compounds that can interact

with certain medications, further highlighting the importance of mindful consumption. To ensure optimal treatment outcomes, it's advisable to adhere to healthcare recommendations regarding beverage consumption while taking medication and to consult with a healthcare professional if unsure. Ultimately, prioritizing informed choices regarding beverage consumption can contribute to better health outcomes and overall well-being.

References

1. National library of Medicine